

Rapid Post-Disaster Waste Management Assessment: Insights from Typhoon Kalmaegi (2025) Flooding in Talisay City, Cebu, Philippines

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Abstract. Flooding can generate sudden debris loads that overwhelm local solid waste management systems, obstruct access, delay cleanup, and create additional recovery challenges. This study developed and applied a rapid post-disaster waste management assessment for riverine flood-affected areas within the Mananga River corridor in Talisay City, Cebu, following the 2025 Typhoon Kalmaegi (Tino). The approach combined rapid field assessment, flood modeling, debris estimation, and a segment criticality index for prioritizing debris clearing and management. Results showed that the reconstructed flood extent reached about 259 ha, exceeding the 195 ha indicated by the reference 25-year flood hazard map within the study area. Field observations showed mixed debris conditions, including mud, sediments, household items, construction materials, vegetation, and other residuals. Estimated debris ranged from 16.8–33.9 thousand metric tons, equivalent to 15–31 thousand m³ or 3.0–6.1 months of municipal solid waste generation, requiring 2.4–4.8 thousand six-wheeler truck trips. Downstream Segment 5 ranked highest for debris management, followed by upstream Segments 2 and 1. The study shows that rapid, field-informed assessment can support early planning, hauling, temporary storage, prioritization, and coordination among local governments in flood-prone areas.

Keywords: Disaster Risk Reduction and Management; Disaster Waste Management; Flood Debris; Talisay City (Cebu); Typhoon Kalmaegi (Tino)

1. Introduction

Disasters triggered by natural hazards, such as floods, typhoons, earthquakes, and tsunamis, can generate large amounts of debris within a short period of time, sometimes at levels far beyond ordinary municipal solid waste generation. This sudden debris volume, especially in severely affected areas, can overwhelm local solid waste management systems and interfere with disaster response and recovery operations [1, 2]. In flood-affected communities, debris is not only the residual materials deposited by floodwaters. If not managed promptly and properly, it can also become a secondary management problem as damaged materials and mixed waste can limit road access, delay rescue and cleanup, block drainage flow paths, and create further environmental and public health risks [1, 3–5]. For this reason, disaster waste management (DWM) becomes a critical part of post-disaster response and recovery rather than a simple cleanup activity after the event.

This issue is particularly important in the Philippines, where typhoons, intense rainfall, and recurrent flooding continue to shape the country's risk landscape being situated in the Pacific typhoon belt. About 20 tropical cyclones enter the Philippine Area of Responsibility (PAR) each year [6], repeatedly exposing communities, infrastructure, and local service systems to damage and disruption. With climate change expected to intensify weather conditions, disaster risk in the country is shaped not only by the frequency of these hazards, but also by the vulnerabilities that influence who is most affected and how difficult recovery becomes. Recent global risk assessments likewise show that the impacts of flood and other crises are not distributed evenly across society, and are often more severe among disadvantaged groups with fewer resources and limited coping capacity [7–10].

The importance of this broader national risk became more evident in 2025, when storms, monsoon floods, and other related hydrometeorological events accounted for a large share of the country's disaster burden, representing about 92% of the cumulative number of people affected by disasters. Among these events, Typhoon Kalmaegi (locally known as Tino) was one of the major disaster events of the year. It crossed PAR from 2 to 6 November 2025, and affected about 5.5 million people nationwide, or roughly 20% of the year's cumulative population affected by hydrometeorological hazards [11]. Cebu Province, within Region VII (Central Visayas), was among the severely affected areas, with widespread impacts on people, housing, infrastructure, and basic services [12]. Available records also indicate unusually intense rainfall and severe flood conditions in Cebu during the event. Mactan synoptic station, one of the primary synoptic stations in Cebu, recorded 183 mm of rain within 24 hours, exceeding the normal total rainfall for the month of November [13, 14]. In Talisay City, one of the most affected urban areas in Metro Cebu, riverine flooding displaced families and left extensive debris and mud along inundated communities, making post-flood clearing and waste management an immediate local concern [15].

Despite the recognized importance of DWM, practical approaches for rapidly quantifying post-disaster debris and translating those estimates into operational planning remain limited, particularly in developing countries such as the Philippines, where guidance and legal frameworks are still evolving [2, 3, 16]. Existing post-disaster reporting and assessment tools in the country, including situational reports, rapid damage assessment and needs analysis (RDANA), and post-disaster needs assessment (PDNA), are useful for documenting affected populations, damaged assets, service disruptions, and recovery needs; however, they are not primarily designed to provide the debris weight or volume information needed for immediate, data-driven decisions on clearance, temporary storage, transport requirements, equipment, personnel, and disposal or recovery pathways [12, 17–19]. Disaster and demolition waste management has also been included as one of the annexes to the annotated outline for the renewal of the 10-year solid waste management plans of local government units (LGUs), but national and local guidance for developing and implementing DWM plans remains limited [16, 20]. These gaps highlight the need for rapid, practical, and locally applicable approaches that can generate usable waste-related information immediately after flood events and support early post-disaster decision-making.

In response to this need, this study aims to develop and apply a rapid post-disaster waste management assessment for riverine flood-affected areas using Talisay City, Cebu as a case study after Typhoon Kalmaegi. Specifically, the study seeks to assess post-flood conditions and debris-related impacts, estimate the quantity of flood-related debris, identify priority areas for debris clearing and management, and derive practical implications for post-disaster waste management planning and local operations. By combining field observations with spatial and estimation-based analyses, the study offers a rapid and field-informed assessment approach and demonstrates its application in a riverine flood-affected city. The findings are intended to provide practical insights that may help local governments strengthen preparedness, support early response decisions, and improve recovery planning in similar flood-prone settings.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study area and event context

This study focused on the Mananga River basin in Talisay City, Cebu Province, Philippines (Figure 1). The Mananga River is one of the main river systems affecting Talisay City and was the principal catchment considered in this assessment of riverine flood impacts. The river originates from the upland and mountainous areas of Cebu City, flows southward through Talisay, and eventually discharges into Bohol Sea at Barangay Biasong. The main channel extends for more than 30 km and drains a catchment of about 8,494 ha. The basin is characterized by mixed land uses, with upstream areas largely dominated by pasture and agriculture, and downstream reaches becoming more urbanized as the river passes through developed parts of the city [21–23]. Based on the 2025 projected city population using the 2024 census and the average annual growth rate between census periods of 2020 and 2024, the city had an estimated population of about 264,017, of which around 82,614 or 31% were estimated to live within the basin [24, 25]. These characteristics make the basin a relevant setting for examining how river flooding in an urbanized watershed can lead to debris accumulation, access constraints, and pressure on local waste management and recovery operations.

Figure 1. Map of Talisay City, Cebu, Philippines (study area).

The event context considered in this study was the riverine flooding associated with Typhoon Kalmaegi in November 2025. The overflow of the Mananga River caused severe flooding along the floodplain and affected densely settled communities within the study area [15]. Because the impacts were concentrated along a major river in a densely settled urban setting, Talisay City provided a suitable case for assessing post-flood debris generation, accumulation, and the resulting management pressures during early recovery.

2.2. Methodological framework

This study adopted an integrated rapid post-disaster waste management assessment framework that combined qualitative field observations with quantitative spatial and estimation-based analyses (Figure 2). The framework was informed by existing disaster waste management literature [5, 26], national policy and institutional frameworks [27–29], and international guidance [30–33] that collectively emphasize the need to link assessment, estimation, coordination, and planning in support of effective post-disaster waste management. The framework covered rapid field assessment for documenting post-flood conditions, flood modeling, debris estimation, debris severity mapping and priority analysis, and planning and operational analysis. These components were designed to build on one another, with field observations supporting flood reconstruction, flood outputs informing debris estimation and prioritization, and all analytical results being synthesized to guide planning and operational implications for local governments.

Figure 2. Methodological framework of the study.

2.3. Rapid field assessment

A rapid field assessment was conducted on 20 November 2025, 16 days after the flood event in Talisay City, to document residual flood evidence and immediate post-flood conditions along the Mananga River basin. Eight key waypoints were pre-selected along the river based on reported flood-affected locations identified from news coverage and social media posts prior to the site visit. Field data were collected and logged using QField to support georeferenced documentation of site observations (see supplementary material). This approach allowed the assessment to focus on locations where flooding and debris impacts were reported to be most visible, while also providing a consistent field record for subsequent flood reconstruction and spatial analysis.

At each waypoint, the assessment documented high-water marks (HWMs), observed debris conditions, visible damage indicators, river and drainage conditions, and reported access to basic services after the flood. Supporting photographs were taken to capture the physical condition of affected areas and to aid later interpretation of debris severity and distribution. Informal interviews and site-based validation with residents and debris clearing workers were also used to confirm flood depths, local damage and debris conditions, and post-flood clearing realities observed during the fieldwork. At least one respondent was interviewed at each waypoint, and no personal information was collected.

2.4. Flood modeling

Flood conditions were reconstructed on a two-dimensional model based on the HWM depths documented during the rapid field assessment using the Hydrologic Engineering Center’s River Analysis System (HEC-RAS), a hydraulic modeling software commonly used to simulate flood behavior and generate inundation maps [34]. An available Digital Terrain Model (DTM) derived from Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (IfSAR) topographic data was used as the main terrain input to represent ground elevation within the study area [22]. The observed HWMs served as the primary

event-based reference for calibrating the model by adjusting simulated water surface elevations to match observed flood levels along the river and adjacent floodplain [34, 35]. The resulting model outputs were processed to derive the spatial extent of inundation and corresponding flood depth.

To assess the reasonableness of the reconstructed flood pattern, the modeled flood extent was cross-checked against the existing 25-year flood hazard map of the University of the Philippines Nationwide Operational Assessment of Hazards (UP NOAH) [36]. The 25-year hazard map was used as a secondary reference as available records during Typhoon Kalmaegi indicated event conditions exceeding the 20-year return period at a nearby synoptic station [13]. This comparison was intended as a consistency check rather than a formal validation against design-event mapping, since the objective of the model was to reconstruct the observed Typhoon Kalmaegi flood event for analytical use in the post-disaster waste assessment.

2.5. Debris estimation

Flood-related debris quantities were estimated by combining the reconstructed flood extent and the UP NOAH 25-year flood hazard map with exposure information and a context-adjusted debris generation rate. The estimation was guided by the rapid disaster waste estimation approach of the Japan Society of Material Cycles and Waste Management (JSMCWM), which estimates debris quantity from the number of damaged buildings and a disaster waste generation intensity. When detailed post-disaster building-by-building damage data are not yet available, the number of affected buildings can be approximated using spatial proxies and the extent of the affected area (Equation 1) [26, 37]. In this study, flood extents with depths greater than or equal to 0.5 m, representing areas with at least moderate flood hazard [36], were considered. These extents were intersected in QGIS with gridded WorldPop (~100-m resolution) population data (279,963) adjusted to match the 2025 projected population of Talisay City (264,017) [24, 25]. Population within the affected area was then converted to the number of affected buildings using an average occupancy of 4.1 persons/building [38]. This approach was adopted because a complete post-flood inventory of damaged structures was not available during the rapid assessment period, and a population-based proxy allowed debris quantities to be estimated in a transparent way for early planning.

$$DW = \frac{P_D}{O} \times A_A \times G \quad (1)$$

where DW is the estimated amount of disaster waste (t), P_D is the population density (persons/km²), O is the average occupancy per building (persons/building), A_A is the extent of affected area (km²), and G is the debris generation rate (t/building).

A debris generation rate of 6–21 t/building was adopted to represent mixed flood debris under local conditions. This range was derived from Philippine post-disaster experience, particularly estimates associated with Typhoon Haiyan/Yolanda (2013), by relating reported debris quantities to the number of affected families or affected buildings [39, 40]. This range was considered more suitable than the lower reference value of 2 t/building used in other flood cases, which mainly reflects household contents only such as furniture and appliances [37]. A site-informed intermediate value of 7 t/building (high-level estimate) was also considered as a sediment-inclusive local reference based on field interviews with debris-clearing workers, who estimated recent hauled volumes from truck trips during cleanup operations. This value was treated as a local reference point rather than a fixed measured rate, recognizing that the field assessment was conducted after initial clearing had already started in some areas. Final outputs were expressed as total weight (t), equivalent volume (m³), and the corresponding number of truck trips. A bulk density assumption of 1.1 t/m³ was used as a conservative planning assumption for mixed, sediment-laden debris, considering the observed presence of mud, sediments, construction materials, and damaged concrete or masonry-related components along the flooded areas [41]. Truck trips were estimated based on a six-wheeler truck with an assumed capacity of 8 m³ and a 20% fill reduction to account for void losses during loading [32].

Uncertainty was addressed through Monte Carlo simulation with 10,000 iterations. The debris generation rate applied a triangular distribution (6-7-21 t/building). The number of affected buildings was varied based on the range derived from the HWM-based reconstructed flood extent and the UP NOAA flood extent. This produced a distribution of possible debris quantities rather than a single deterministic value. The resulting estimates were summarized using the 10th percentile (P10) and 90th percentile (P90) as lower and upper planning bounds, respectively, to reflect the uncertainty associated with both debris generation rates and the affected extent during rapid post-disaster assessment.

2.6. Debris severity mapping and priority analysis

A segment criticality index (SCI) was developed to identify priority areas for debris clearing and management along the flood-affected river corridor. The corridor was divided into five segments using major roads and bridges as practical boundaries. This segmentation was adopted because these features can serve as recognizable reference points for field validation, access planning, and cleanup sequencing. The SCI combined three planning-relevant indicators within each segment, including debris severity, flood depth, and exposed population. Each indicator was then normalized using min–max scaling to allow comparison across different units and ranges. The SCI was calculated as the average of the normalized values within each segment, giving equal weight to observed debris condition, flood severity, and population exposure (Equation 2). Equal weighting was applied to maintain a simple prioritization. Higher SCI values indicate segments where debris clearing and management may require earlier attention due to the combined presence of visible debris impacts, deeper flooding, and greater exposed population. The resulting ranking was used as a decision-support output for identifying priority segments for early clearing, temporary containment, and post-disaster waste management planning.

$$SCI_i = \frac{D_i + F_i + E_i}{3} \quad (2)$$

where SCI_i is the segment criticality index for segment i , D_i is the normalized mean debris severity score computed from the product of the debris footprint and debris distribution scores across photo-documented observations within segment i , F_i is the normalized flood depth indicator, and E_i is the normalized exposed population.

Each SCI indicator for each segment was derived from a specific data source to reflect both observed field conditions and modeled flood exposure. Debris severity was assessed using field photographs and site observations collected during the rapid field assessment. The simple scoring considered the visible debris footprint and distribution (Table 1). Segment-level debris severity was calculated from the mean product of the footprint and distribution scores across photo-documented observations within each segment (see supplementary material). The flood depth represented the physical intensity of inundation and was based on the 90th percentile flood depth outside the river channel to reduce possible effects of artifacts due to channel alignment and terrain data. Exposed population considered the total number of people within the mapped flood extent.

Table 1. Debris severity scoring for debris footprint and distribution.

Component	Score	Description
Debris footprint	0	No visible debris or clean banks and streets
	1	Debris line along riverbanks
	2	Debris visible on floodplains
	3	Debris affecting roads, paths, drainage, or access
Debris distribution	1	Scattered/thin (no piles; clearing is mostly sweeping/collection)
	2	Visible/dense piles (requires repeated trips or mechanical clearing)

2.7. Planning and operational analysis

To translate results into practical implications for post-disaster waste management, field observations, modeled flood characteristics, debris quantity estimates, and SCI-based priority rankings were synthesized. The interpretation considered how flood depth, debris accumulation, exposed population, and observed field conditions may affect early clearing, access, temporary containment, hauling requirements, and pressure on local waste management facilities. Field observations on debris-clearing activities, access constraints, and affected service conditions were used to ground the analysis in actual post-flood conditions rather relying only on modeled outputs. The resulting insights were used to identify planning considerations for local governments, including priority clearing areas, transport and equipment needs, documentation of debris transfer, and preparedness measures that can support faster and more organized recovery after similar flood events in the future.

2.8. Assumptions and limitations

This study operates under several key assumptions to support rapid post-disaster waste estimation and prioritization. The field assessment was assumed to provide sufficient representative post-flood evidence for the selected river corridor, although observations were limited to eight waypoints based on reported flooding from upstream to downstream and were conducted 16 days after the flood event due to resource constraints. The HWM-based flood reconstruction was assumed to reasonably represent the observed riverine flood conditions, with the UP NOAA 25-year flood hazard map used as a secondary spatial reference. The debris estimation also assumed that population within areas with flood depths greater than or equal to 0.5 m could be used as a proxy for affected buildings, using the adjusted population spatial data and average occupancy per building. Due to the limited availability of locally applicable data and guidelines, the adopted debris generation rates, bulk density, and truck capacity assumptions were treated as planning parameters to estimate debris weight, volume, and hauling requirements. For the priority analysis, the debris severity scoring was assumed to adequately represent visible debris conditions within each segment based on field photographs and observations.

Despite these measures, the study has notable limitations. The rapid field assessment focused on areas where visible evidence of riverine flood damage remained during the visit and may not have covered all actual affected locations. In addition, some debris may have already been removed before the site visit, which may affect the interpretation of observed debris severity and clearing conditions. Interviews with affected locals may also be affected by recall, perception, and personal experience. The flood model was intended to reconstruct the considered event for analytical use and was not a detailed engineering flood study; therefore, results may still be influenced by HWM uncertainty, terrain resolution, channel representation, and the treatment of local hydraulic features. Similarly, the debris estimates should be interpreted as rapid planning estimates rather than a complete post-disaster waste inventory, especially given the limited availability of truck logs and weighing records. Uncertainty also remains in the debris generation rates, affected population estimates, population-to-building proxy assumptions, bulk density, truck capacity assumptions, segment boundaries, equal weighting of SCI indicators, and semi-quantitative scoring of debris conditions which relied on engineering judgment of authors based on field photographs and observations. These limitations define the appropriate use of the results, which are to support early planning, prioritization, and operational decision-making, rather than to replace detailed field inventories, engineering assessments, or final accounting of disaster waste quantities.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Flood characteristics and inundation pattern

The reconstructed flood extent indicates that Typhoon Kalmaegi produced widespread riverine flooding along the Mananga River corridor, with stronger inundation toward downstream portion of the river (Figure 3). The HWM-based flood model estimated an inundated area of about 259 ha, which was larger than the 195 ha indicated by the UP NOAH 25-year flood hazard map within the same area. This difference suggests that the observed event produced a wider flood footprint than the reference hazard map in several parts of the study area, particularly in the downstream barangays of Biasong and Dumlog and in portions of Lawaan II and San Isidro. The difference, however, was not uniform across the corridor, as some upstream and midstream barangays showed comparable or larger mapped areas in the UP NOAH reference. This indicates that the event was not only extensive, but also spatially uneven in how inundation expanded across the river catchment.

Figure 3. Flood characteristics and inundation pattern of Typhoon Kalmaegi in Talisay City, Cebu. (a) HWM-based flood map; (b) UP NOAH 25-year flood hazard map; (c) Barangay-level inundated area comparison.

Flood depth results further show that the event involved both deep channel flooding and substantial floodplain inundation. Channel flood depths exceeded approximately 10 m in parts of the modeled river section, while floodplain inundated reach about 5–6 m in severely affected areas. These depths help explain the observed movement and deposition of mud, household contents, vegetation, and other mixed debris after the flood. Although embankments are intended to reduce or prevent flooding in protected areas [42], the downstream expansion of flooding was consistent with reported damage to or overtopping of flood-control structures [15]. These conditions may have allowed floodwaters and transported materials to spread into nearby settled areas, including informal riverside communities that are highly vulnerable to flooding [43]. From a DWM perspective, this pattern is important because deeper and wider inundation can increase debris generation, mobilize waste across longer distances, block access routes, and concentrate cleanup needs in downstream communities. Thus, the flood map provides the physical basis for understanding where debris-related impacts were likely to accumulate and where early clearing and management actions would be most needed.

3.2. Debris conditions, types, and operational observations

The rapid field assessment showed that flooding associated with Typhoon Kalmaegi substantially changed the type, amount, and distribution of waste along the Mananga River corridor. Based on site-based observations and local accounts (n = 18), pre-flood debris was generally described as limited, with respondents reporting only small amounts of debris in most of the waypoints (6/8) before the event (Figure 4). After the flood, however, large debris accumulations were observed across all photo-documented post-flood waypoints (8/8). This suggests that the event did not only redistribute existing waste along the river, but also generated and mobilized additional materials from flooded households, damaged structures, riverbanks, and surrounding open areas.

Figure 4. Observed post-flood debris conditions along the Mananga River corridor based on rapid field assessment. Pie charts indicate the share of the number of interviewed residents who observed and reported each debris type at each waypoint; they do not represent composition by weight.

Observed debris was mixed and heterogeneous, which is typical of post-flood waste conditions [30–32]. Pre-flood debris was mainly reported to consist of plastics and wood, which expanded to mud and sediments, household items, construction materials, vegetative waste, and other mixed residuals after the flood. The presence of mud and sediment was especially challenging because these materials increased the volume and weight of debris, complicated manual clearing, and reduced the efficiency of ordinary waste collection. Debris was also observed along riverbanks, near bridges, beside roads, and within affected communities, showing that floodwaters transported materials across the floodplain and deposited them in areas where they could obstruct access, drainage, and cleanup operations.

Field observations and informal interviews also highlighted operational challenges during early disaster response and recovery. Clearing support appeared uneven across affected locations, with some upstream communities reportedly relying on self-clearing for more than two weeks after the flood, aggravated by limited support and available equipment for clearing [15]. In some areas, debris was temporarily placed along roadsides, open spaces, or informal collection points while awaiting removal. These conditions suggest that the current regular weekly waste collection services, as reported locally, were not designed to sufficiently absorb the sudden debris surge created by the flood. The absence of trash traps and irregular pre-flood cleanups may have also contributed to debris movement and deposition, although this should be interpreted as a field-based observation rather than a quantified causal relationship. These findings show that post-flood debris is not only a material quantity problem, but also an operational issue involving access, temporary storage, hauling capacity, and coordination [5].

3.3. Debris quantity estimates and implications for SWM capacity

The estimated debris quantities show that the Typhoon Kalmaegi flood generated a sudden waste burden that was substantial relative to the normal municipal solid waste flow of Talisay City. Based on the estimated affected population of 10,937, and the estimated 2,315 affected buildings within the mapped flood extent, the full debris estimate ranged from about 14 to 49 thousand metric tons using the adopted unit generation rates. After uncertainty treatment, the Monte Carlo simulation provided a narrower planning range of about 16.8 to 33.9 thousand metric tons between the 10th and 90th percentiles. Using the assumed bulk density of 1.1 t/m³, this corresponds to approximately 15 to 31 thousand m³ of debris, requiring 2.4 to 4.8 thousand six-wheeler truck trips. These figures should be interpreted as rapid planning estimates rather than final inventory values, but they provide a useful indication of the scale of debris that needed to be cleared, transported, temporarily stored, or disposed after the flood.

When compared with the city’s projected municipal solid waste generation of about 184.81 t/day in 2025 [44], the estimated flood debris based on the Monte Carlo planning range is equivalent to roughly 3.0 to 6.1 months of regular municipal solid waste generation. This comparison is important because it translates the disaster waste into a scale that local waste managers can more easily interpret. Even the lower estimate represents several months of regular waste generation arriving within a short recovery period, while the upper estimate would place significant pressure on collection, hauling, temporary storage, and disposal systems. If most of this debris were directed to disposal without prior segregation, recovery, or volume reduction, it could consume a large share of available landfill capacity and further strain waste facilities that are already operating under limited space.

Compared with selected hydrometeorological disaster waste records, the Talisay estimate is lower than the reported debris volumes from the 2009 Typhoon Ketsana in Marikina City and the 2014 Typhoon Rammasun in Pasig City, but it remains substantial when viewed against local waste management capacity for an urban flood event (Table 2). The comparison with national-scale events, such as the 2013 Super Typhoon Haiyan, the 2011 Thailand flooding, and the 2016 Tropical Cyclone Winston in Fiji, also helps place the estimate in a wider disaster waste context. These larger events show how hydrometeorological disasters can generate debris at regional or national scales, while the Talisay

case highlights how localized riverine flooding can still create a concentrated waste management burden for a single city. It should be noted that the values from other events are reported as published and should therefore be interpreted as indicative, as estimation methods, spatial scales, waste definitions, and inclusion of sediments may differ across sources. Overall, the comparison reinforces that post-flood debris management requires temporary storage planning, additional hauling support, rapid transfer to recovery or disposal sites, and coordination with nearby local governments and private service providers during early recovery [4, 5, 30, 31].

Table 2. Comparison of estimated flood-related debris in Talisay City (Typhoon Kalmaegi) with selected disaster waste quantities from previous hydrometeorological events.

Event (Year)	Location	Estimated disaster waste		Equivalent or context	Source
		Weight (metric tons)	Volume (m ³)		
Typhoon Kalmaegi / Tino (2025)	Talisay City, Cebu, Philippines (Mananga River)	16,800–33,900	15,000–31,000	~3.0–6.1 months of local MSW	This study
Typhoon Rammasun / Glenda (2014)	Pasig City, Philippines	Not reported	47,668	~15 days of local MSW	[45]
Typhoon Ketsana / Ondoy (2009)	Marikina City, Philippines	Not reported	95,000	~50 days of local MSW	[45]
Super Typhoon Haiyan / Yolanda (2013)	Philippines	19,000,000	Not reported	National-scale disaster waste	[31]
Tropical Cyclone Winston (2016)	Fiji	23,525	Not reported	National-scale disaster waste	[31]
Various flooding (2011)	Thailand	152,000	Not reported	National-scale disaster waste	[33]
Joso Flooding (2015)	Joso City, Japan	52,000	Not reported	~3 years of local MSW	[31]
Hiroshima Flood and Landslides (2014)	Hiroshima City, Japan	584,000	Not reported	~1.6 years of local MSW	[31]

3.4. Priority segments for debris clearing and management

The SCI results identified downstream Segment 5 as the area with the highest priority for debris clearing and management, followed by upstream segments 2 and 1 (Figure 5). Segment 5 recorded the highest SCI value (SCI = 0.663), mainly due to the combined influence of high debris severity and the largest

exposed population within the mapped flood extent. This result reflects the severity of downstream conditions, where substantial debris and mud deposition were still observed 16 days after the flood. Segment 2 ranked second (SCI = 0.548), largely because it recorded the highest 90th percentile flood depth outside the river channel which likely affected the vulnerable communities who may be living in such areas, while Segment 1 ranked third (SCI = 0.532) due to its high exposed population and observed debris conditions. The high ranking of the upstream segments is also consistent with field accounts indicating limited support and equipment availability in some affected communities to facilitate debris clearing. These results indicate that priority areas were not defined by debris visibility alone, but by the combined presence of debris severity, flood intensity, and population exposure.

Figure 5. Segment criticality index (SCI) results for prioritizing debris clearing and management along the Mananga River corridor as assessed on 20 November 2025 (16 days post-flood).

The ranking also helped distinguished between areas with visible debris and areas with higher operational criticality. For instance, Segment 4 recorded the highest debris severity score, but ranked fourth because it had the lowest exposed population among the segments. Segment 3 ranked lowest despite having moderate debris severity because its combined flood depth and exposure indicators were lower than those of the higher-ranked segments. This shows the value of using a combined index for rapid early decision making, as visually severe debris conditions may not always correspond to the highest overall priority when exposure and flood intensity are considered as well.

From an operational perspective, the SCI results can support the sequencing of cleanup and resource allocation during early recovery. Higher-ranked segments may require earlier clearing, additional hauling support, temporary containment areas, and closer coordination with barangays, city waste management personnel, and nearby waste disposal or processing facilities. The results should be interpreted as a rapid planning guide rather than a final prioritization of all affected areas, since the scoring was based on field conditions observed during the survey period. Nevertheless, the SCI provides a practical way to identify where limited clearing resources may be directed first, especially when local governments need to make early decisions before a full debris inventory is available.

3.5. Implications for post-disaster waste management planning and local operations

The findings show that post-flood debris management should be planned before disasters occur, not treated only as a cleanup activity after flooding. In the Philippines, DWM is still addressed mainly through the intersection of solid waste management, disaster risk reduction and management, and related local planning frameworks, rather than through a dedicated national DWM system [27–29]. This makes local preparedness especially important [4, 5, 16]. For flood-prone cities such as Talisay, the results indicate the need to integrate disaster debris scenarios, temporary storage sites, hauling routes, equipment requirements, and disposal or recovery options into local SWM and DRRM plans.

The rapid assessment approach used in this study can support early decision-making when complete waste inventories are not yet available. Field observations helped identify the types and location of debris, flood modeling showed where debris-related impacts were likely to concentrate, debris estimates translated the event into hauling and disposal requirements, and the SCI helped identify where clearing may need to be prioritized. Together, these outputs provide practical information that local governments can use to estimate required trucks, identify temporary containment or transfer areas, sequence clearing operations, and coordinate with contractors, disposal facilities, and neighboring LGUs.

Several operational lessons also emerged from the assessment. First, temporary storage and collection points should be pre-identified, permitted, and mapped near flood-prone areas, but away from areas that may obstruct drainage, access roads, or evacuation routes [30, 42]. Second, clearing operations should also be standardized through simple documentation systems, including truck logs, load tickets, and debris characterization records, to improve tracking and reduce uncertainty in post-disaster estimates [30]. Third, where feasible, mixed debris should be segregated to separate recoverable materials, sediment, vegetative waste, bulky household items, and residuals for appropriate recovery or disposal [30, 31, 42]. Fourth, routine pre-flood cleanups, desilting, and maintenance of debris interceptors or trash traps near bridges and culverts before the rainy season may also reduce the amount of loose material transported during floods [33, 42, 46]. Lastly, these measures should also be supported by socio-behavioral change communication (SBCC) in waste management and DRRM, together with adequate infrastructure, equipment, and enforcement to promote safe debris handling, reporting, segregation, and protection of drainage and river corridors [47, 48].

More broadly, the study highlights the value of linking technical assessment with operational planning. Rapid debris estimation and priority mapping cannot replace a full post-disaster waste inventory, but they can provide enough information to guide early action while detailed assessments are still being prepared. For data-scarce and flood-prone LGUs, this approach offers a practical starting point for improving contingency planning, resource allocation, and inter-agency coordination. It also shows that effective DWM requires more than hauling waste after a disaster; it requires prior planning, clear documentation systems, prepared temporary storage options, coordinated institutional roles, and community-level participation supported by appropriate infrastructure and services.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study applied a rapid post-disaster waste management assessment to the riverine flooding within Mananga River corridor associated with Typhoon Kalmaegi in Talisay City, Cebu. The findings show that post-flood debris is a significant waste management and disaster recovery issue, not simply a cleanup concern after floodwaters recede. The rapid assessment approach provided practical evidence for early decision-making by linking field observations, flood mapping, debris estimation and priority ranking into one planning-oriented framework. This type of assessment provides local governments with a practical basis for faster and more informed decisions on the early identification of temporary storage sites or collection points, hauling and equipment requirements, priority clearing areas, and coordination needs with both the public and private sectors, while also reducing the likelihood that unmanaged debris will worsen access, drainage, and future flood-related risks. Its value is especially relevant in

flood-prone and data-scarce settings, where complete post-disaster waste inventories are often unavailable during the early response and recovery period but decisions on clearing, transport, and disposal must still be made immediately.

Based on the findings, there is a need to strengthen prevention, preparedness, accountability, risk reduction, and governance in post-disaster waste management. Local governments and key sectors should coordinate early to ensure safer waste recovery and disposal. Rapid post-disaster waste assessment should be integrated into local disaster preparedness, solid waste management, and recovery planning. Future work should validate rapid estimates against actual post-disaster waste inventories, test the approach in other flood-prone local governments, adapt it in other hazard contexts, and refine the method by improving local debris generation factors, adding relevant priority SCI indicators (e.g., accessibility constraints, presence of vulnerable populations, proximity to critical facilities, presence of hazardous materials, etc.), and strengthening the spatial resolution of analysis. These steps can help move disaster waste management from reactive cleanup toward a more anticipatory, evidence-based, and locally actionable practice.

Data Availability Statement

All secondary datasets used in this study are publicly available online, with sources cited in the Methodology section. Geospatial outputs and derived data generated from this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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References

1. Brown C, Milke M, Seville E (2011) Disaster waste management: A review article. *Waste Management* 31:1085–1098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2011.01.027>
2. Poudel R, Hirai Y, Asari M, Sakai S (2018) Establishment of unit generation rates of building debris in Kathmandu Valley, Nepal, after the Gorkha earthquake. *J Mater Cycles Waste Manag* 20:1663–1675. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-018-0731-8>
3. Fernandez G, Asari M, Uy N, et al (2023) Developing capacity for post-typhoon disaster waste management in Lautoka, Fiji, and Makati, Philippines. *APN SCI BULL* 13. <https://doi.org/10.30852/sb.2023.2226>
4. Tajima R, Hirayama N, Osako M (2014) Theory and practice of pre-disaster planning for disaster waste management. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Theory-and-practice-of-pre-disaster-planning-for-Tajima-Hirayama/471e09f5844ccb80f5b7e55fe77b4e47f5743e36>. Accessed 19 April 2026
5. Tajima R, Tsuji T, Suzuki K, Muhamad AF (2023) Conceptualizing disaster waste governance using network governance perspectives. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 99:104137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2023.104137>

6. PAGASA (2025) Tropical Cyclone Information - Overview. In: Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical, and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA). <https://www.pagasa.dost.gov.ph/climate/tropical-cyclone-information>. Accessed 18 April 2026
7. Bündnis Entwicklung Hilft / IFHV (2025) WorldRiskReport 2025. Berlin: Bündnis Entwicklung Hilft. <https://weltrisikobericht.de/worldriskreport/#>. Accessed 18 April 2026
8. Bündnis Entwicklung Hilft / IFHV (2024) WorldRiskReport 2024. Berlin: Bündnis Entwicklung Hilft. <https://weltrisikobericht.de/worldriskreport/#>. Accessed 18 April 2026
9. Bündnis Entwicklung Hilft / IFHV (2023) WorldRiskReport 2023. Berlin: Bündnis Entwicklung Hilft. <https://weltrisikobericht.de/worldriskreport/#>. Accessed 18 April 2026
10. Bündnis Entwicklung Hilft / IFHV (2022) WorldRiskReport 2022. Berlin: Bündnis Entwicklung Hilft. <https://weltrisikobericht.de/worldriskreport/#>. Accessed 18 April 2026
11. UN OCHA (2026) Philippines 2025 Year in Review: Significant Disaster Trends and Events. <https://reliefweb.int/report/philippines/philippines-2025-year-review-significant-disaster-trends-and-events>. Accessed 18 April 2026
12. NDRRMC (2025) Situational Report No. 30 for the Effects of Tropical Cyclone Tino (2025). National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), Quezon City. https://ndrrmc.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/Situational_Report_No._30_for_the_Effects_of_Tropical_Cyclone_TINO_2025.pdf. Accessed 18 April 2026
13. Rojas A (2025) Tino dumps more than a month's rain in Southern Leyte, Cebu. ABS-CBN News. <https://www.abs-cbn.com/news/weather-traffic/2025/11/4/tino-dumps-more-than-a-month-s-rain-in-southern-leyte-cebu-1320>. Accessed 25 November 2025
14. PAGASA (2024) Climatological Normals - Mactan Station
15. Datu D (2025) Tino wipes out riverside communities in Talisay City. ABS-CBN News. <https://www.abs-cbn.com/news/regions/2025/11/7/tino-wipes-out-riverside-communities-in-talisay-city-0816>. Accessed 19 April 2026
16. Higashi S (2024) Exploring Guidelines for Disaster Waste Management in Southeast Asia. *Global Environmental Research* 28: 11-16. https://doi.org/10.57466/ger.28.1_11
17. NDRRMC (2014) Guidelines in the Conduct of Rapid Damage Assessment and Needs Analysis (RDANA) - Memorandum Circular No. 25, s.2014
18. Alegre L (2015) PDNA in the Philippines: Generating Results and Lessons Learned. <https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/files/Ms.%20Alegre%20-%20PDNA-Lessons%20Learned%20UNESCAP%2027Oct2015.pdf>. Accessed 18 April 2026
19. NDRRMC (2021) NDRRMC Rapid Damage Assessment and Needs Analysis (RDANA) Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) - Memorandum No. 107, s. 2021
20. NSWMC (2024) Resolution Adopting the Annexes to the Annotated Outline for the Renewal of 10-Year Solid Waste Management Plans of Local Government Units - NSWMC Resolution No. 1655, Series of 2024
21. DENR-EMB Region 7 (2025) Regional State of the Brown Environment Report 2024 Central Visayas. Environmental Management Bureau Region 7, Mandaue City. <https://r7.emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/2024-RSOBE-Report-Region-7.pdf>. Accessed 18 April 2026
22. NAMRIA (2013) Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar - Digital Terrain Model - Cebu (10 m) [Dataset]. National Mapping and Resource Information Authority (NAMRIA)
23. NAMRIA (2022) 2020 Land Cover Map of Central Visayas Region [Dataset]. Geoportal. National Mapping and Resource Information Authority (NAMRIA)
24. PSA (2025) 2024 Census of Population (POPCEN) - Population and PGR by Region, Province/HUC, and City/Municipality [Dataset]. Philippine Statistics Authority.

- <https://psa.gov.ph/content/2024-census-population-popcen-population-counts-declared-official-president>. Accessed 25 November 2025
25. Bondarenko, M., Kerr, D., Sorichetta, A., Tatem, A.J. (2020) Census/projection-disaggregated gridded population datasets, adjusted to match the corresponding UNPD 2020 estimates, for 183 countries in 2020 using Built-Settlement Growth Model (BSGM) outputs [Dataset]. WorldPop, University of Southampton. <https://doi.org/10.5258/SOTON/WP00685>
 26. JSMCWM (2022) Technical Reference: Estimating the amount of disaster waste generated. Japan Society of Material Cycles and Waste Management (JSMCWM). https://jsmcwm.or.jp/international/files/2022/03/3_Estimating-the-amount-of-disaster-waste-generated.pdf. Accessed 25 November 2025
 27. Republic of the Philippines (2001) Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003). <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2001/01/26/republic-act-no-9003/>. Accessed 18 April 2026
 28. Republic of the Philippines (2009) Climate Change Act of 2009 (RA 9729). <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/phi100134.pdf>. Accessed 18 April 2026
 29. Republic of the Philippines (2010) Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010 (RA 10121). <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2010/05/27/republic-act-no-10121/>. Accessed 18 April 2026
 30. Joint UNEP/OCHA Environment Unit (2013) Disaster Waste Management Guidelines. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/27291>. Accessed 18 April 2026
 31. MOEJ (2018) Disaster Waste Management Guideline for Asia and the Pacific. Ministry of Environment, Japan. https://jsmcwm.or.jp/international/files/2021/03/DWM-guideline_English_2018.pdf. Accessed 25 November 2025
 32. SPREP (2025) Pacific Disaster Waste Management Guideline: Drafting a National Disaster Waste Management Plan (NDWMP) & Estimating Disaster Waste Volumes. Secretariat of the Pacific Regional Environment Programme (SPREP), Apia. <https://library.sprep.org/sites/default/files/2025-07/National-Disaster-Waste-Management-Plan.pdf>. Accessed 18 April 2026
 33. NIES (2015) Flood Waste Management Guidelines for Bangkok. National Institute for Environmental Studies (NIES). <https://www.apn-gcr.org/publication/flood-waste-management-guidelines-for-bangkok/>. Accessed 18 April 2026
 34. USACE Hydrologic Engineering Center (2023) HEC-RAS User's Manual. <https://www.hec.usace.army.mil/software/hec-ras/documentation/HEC-RAS%20User's%20Manual-v6.4.1.pdf>. Accessed 18 April 2026
 35. Qian Q, Edwards DJ, Zhang Y, Haselbach L (2024) Improving Flood Inundation Mapping Accuracy Using HEC-RAS Modeling: A Case Study of the Neches River Tidal Floodplain in Texas. *J Hydrol Eng* 29:05024011. <https://doi.org/10.1061/JHYEFF.HEENG-6037>
 36. UP NOAH (2024) Flood Hazard Maps - Cebu [Dataset]. University of the Philippines Nationwide Operational Assessment of Hazards (UP NOAH). <https://noah.up.edu.ph/>. Accessed 25 November 2025
 37. Kushiya Y (2021) Estimating the amount of Disaster Waste. Japan Society of Material Cycles and Waste Management (JSMCWM). https://jsmcwm.or.jp/international/files/2021/03/DWM_Lecture_Estimating-the-amount.pdf. Accessed 25 November 2025
 38. PSA (2022) 2020 Census of Population and Housing - Household Size of Region VII [Dataset]. Philippine Statistics Authority. <https://psa.gov.ph/content/household-population-number-households-and-average-household-size-philippines-2020-census>. Accessed 25 November 2025

39. NDRRMC (2013) Situational Report No. 64: Effects of Typhoon “Yolanda” (Haiyan). National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), Quezon City
40. NDRRMC (2014) NDRRMC Update Sitrep No. 108 Effects of Typhoon “Yolanda” (Haiyan). National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC), Quezon City
41. Tajima R (2021) Mentoring Session for Makati City Disaster Waste Contingency Planning: Temporary Storage Sites for Disaster Waste Management
42. SPREP (2021) Pacific Island Countries Regional Disaster Waste Management Guideline. Secretariat of the Pacific Regional Environment Programme (SPREP), Apia.
https://library.sprep.org/sites/default/files/2022-02/disaster-waste-management-guideline_0.pdf. Accessed 18 April 2026
43. Bollettino V, Dy P, Alcayna T, Vinck P (2016) DisasterNet Philippines: Scoping Study Report. Cambridge. Harvard Humanitarian Initiative. https://hhi.harvard.edu/sites/g/files/omnuum6866/files/humanitarianinitiative/files/disasternet_philippines_scoping_study_071116.pdf. Accessed 18 April 2026
44. NSWMC (2025) Total Projected Waste Generation [Dataset]. National Solid Waste Management Commission.
<https://app.powerbi.com/view?r=eyJrIjoieMDhiZmU4YzktNzk3Mi00ODIwLWFKNGQtNDIzMWZhNWNiNWNiIiwidCI6ImY2ZjRhNjkyLTQzYjMtNDMzYi05MmlyLTUyYzRlNmNjZDkyMCI6ImMiOjEwfQ%3D%3D>. Accessed 25 November 2025
45. Osorio E, Tandoc FJ, Tanchuling MA, Diola MBL (2017) Assessment of Disaster Waste Management in NCR. UNESCO-JASTIP Joint Symposium on Intra-Regional Water Security and Disaster Management.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/391318978_Assessment_of_Disaster_Waste_Management_in_NCR. Accessed 18 April 2026
46. Wang L, Cui S, Li Y, et al (2022) A review of the flood management: from flood control to flood resilience. *Heliyon* 8:e11763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11763>
47. Treyes AC, Osorio E, Tanchuling MA, et al (2023) Socio-behavioral assessment of household solid waste management: The case of Barangay Calicanto, Philippines. *IOP Conf Ser: Earth Environ Sci* 1257:012008. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1257/1/012008>
48. UNICEF Philippines (2026) Analysis of Social and Behaviour Change Landscape and Capacity in the Philippines. <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/reports/analysis-social-and-behaviour-change-landscape-and-capacity-philippines>. Accessed 27 April 2026

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